

Transparency of Health Toward Bureaucracy Reforms in the Province of North Maluku in 2015

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Abstract: This study aimed to get an overview of the health administrative transparency in the reform of the bureaucracy in the province of North Maluku in 5 health centers at 5 District North Maluku. This study used quantitative analysis survey, and The sample using multistage simple random sampling technique. The low transparency of health administration in the reform of the bureaucracy in the province of North Maluku. Research shows that in the transparency, the majority of respondents still feels the service is open, but do not ignore the other respondents who claimed never to have felt it. Even that has seen no open service access due to the difficulty of access. Standardization costs already felt the majority of respondents in the aspect of transparency of health care costs (78.66%), but do not ignore the opinion of the respondents (18%) claimed lack of transparency in health care costs in the health centers. The idea of change in the bureaucratic system of health center services through transparency of health services at the health center, the majority (93.66%) wanted a system is necessary to change the bureaucratic system more transparent with a wish for Commitment aspects of bureaucratic apparatus in a running system, provide facilities for services, change the behavior of the apparatus in service. Similarly, most respondent eager for health care to the community conducted openly and fairly (50%), Bureaucracy as the engine of government administration should be free from corruption (36%) and Services are concerned with the public interest more important than the interests of the group / private (13, 66%). For this to materialize, the majority of respondents want to be responsible for reform of the health care bureaucracy is a central government / local (82%) and "Private / companies (18%). Necessary to change the bureaucratic system of health center services through transparency of health services for the realization aspects Commitment bureaucratic apparatus in the running system, the urgency of the provision of care facilities, changed the behavior of the apparatus in service in North Maluku. The results of this research may reform health care more transparent administration in the province of North Maluku.

Keywords: health administration Transparency, Reforms

1. Introduction

The study becomes important reforms in the government bureaucracy. This is because the bureaucracy is a state machine that serves to manage the resources in the form of the bureaucratic apparatus, state facilities and budgets to finance and run the bureaucracy. No country is no good without a good bureaucracy, and the bureaucracy will improve the condition of the country and develop. Bureaucratic reform will encourage good governance, improving the quality of public services, capacity building and public accountability. Bureaucratic reforms will improve the professionalism of human resources, enhance good working system and the impact on the competence of the bureaucratic apparatus

comprehensively (Said, 2012).

From a theoretical perspective bureaucratic reform has shifted the issue from one discovery to the next meeting in trigger bureaucratic reforms Issues Democratization (Since 1999) Issues of Good Governance (Since 2000) Issue Autonomous Region (since 2001) Issue Sound Governance (Since 2004) Issue Government of innovative (since 2008) Democratization Issues (since 2008). Meanwhile the issue from a practical perspective triggers bureaucratic reform models can be explained on several concepts that the high demands for efficiency (since 2003) Vision, Mission New Government (since 2004) Corruption and Trust Decline (years to come) Reforms (since 2009). Even up on the latest issues, reform of the bureaucracy that is Dileberative Democracy (Josep Bessette, 1980), Innovative bureaucracy (Alexander Styhre, 2007), Sound Governance (Ali Farazmand 2008), Citizen Drive Change (Steve Goldsmith, 2009).

Issues intensive bureaucratic reform implemented in line with the government's efforts to eradicate corruption in Indonesia. The presence of the Institute of the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) in the era of President Megawati is a strong indication of the political will of the Government of Indonesia for good governance. Based on the data in the world corruption perception index published by Transparency International note that in 2014, globally there are five (5) countries with the highest score of the practice of transparency. These countries are Denmark (92), New Zealand (91), Finland (89), Sweden (87), and Switzerland (86). While the five (5) countries with the lowest score is Somalia (8), North Korea (8), Sudan (11), Afghanistan (12), and South Sudan (15).

Score a sharp decline in the CPI in 2014 experienced by China (with a score of 36), Turkey (45) and Angola (19), where the third country has experienced a sharp decline score, 4-5 points (on a scale of 100). Although it is known that China and Turkey experienced economic growth of over 4% in the last four years. "CPI 2014 shows that economic growth has been undermined by corruption. It is characterized by abuse of power by leaders and high-ranking officials," said José Ugaz, Chairman of Transparency International in Berlin. The corruption perception index ranks Indonesia 107 Of the 175 countries ranked in the world.

Moreover, in the context of any public service, Indonesia bit far from encouraging achievement. While the public service has a strategic role in the implementation of development in Indonesia. As a sovereign and independent country, Indonesia should ensure its citizens to obtain services that meet their needs. In addition to education and health needs, facilities and infrastructure also have a significant influence on the development and advancement of its citizens. As is known, the quality of public services in Indonesia is still low when compared to Asian countries and other Asean. Indonesia's position in the World Competitiveness Yearbook 2014 is in 37th position with a score of 59.6. This position still lags behind its neighboring countries in Asia such as Hong Kong, which exist in the 4-position with a score of 90.3, Taiwan at position 13 with a score of 81.2, Japan at position 21 with a score of 73.8, a neighboring clump of nearby, namely Malaysia, which occupies the 12th position with a score of 82.1, China ranks 23 with a score of 73.3, and Korea at position 26 with a score of 69.7.

In the ASEAN region, Indonesia is still lagging behind compared to Malaysia in 12th position with a score of 82.1, Thailand at position 29 with a score of 65.0 or Singapore, which ranks third in the world with a score of 91.0, far exceeding the country in Asia except for Hong Kong, the difference is only one rank below Singapore. The only strictly sticking Asean neighbors Indonesia is the Philippines is in position 42 with a score of 55.0

When Indonesia's competitiveness on the world stage is still far behind countries in Asia and Asean, In the country itself, Index Governance or Governance among provinces in 2009 showed that the North Maluku province was ranked 31 with a score 4:29 for all provinces in Indonesia. If in 2009 the North

Maluku Province is ranked 31 out of 33 provinces, in 2014, Indonesia Governance Index puts North Maluku Province has 10 districts with the worst ratings in Indonesia, or the order of 33. If the province of North Maluku position 33 or the worst in governance with governance indicators, bureaucracy, civil society, and economic community, then the data are implicitly shown that 10 districts / cities in North Maluku province have low values in government, particularly public services,

To be able to know how the government bureaucracy system of community health centers (puskesmas) in five districts / cities in North Maluku province, require the research process between customers of the health service, better known by the patient. The concept of research on the perception of satisfaction and expectations of the customer / patient health center with five concepts of quality or service quality, known as 5 Quality Service (SERVQUAL) developed by Kotler (2003) dimension of reliability, responsiveness (responsibility), assurance, empathy and tangibles.

2. Literature Review

The general concept of public administration (Caiden, 1991: 97-100). The orientation and reform are in order wanting to set goals, such as targets to be achieved, policies, size, shape, structure, and concentration on the institution.

Administration reform is also referred to as a change of the political system of the nation generally include process changes in the structure or administration of public service procedures, because if this is not done the Implementation of the public service will be stagnant due to social expectations and political environment (Farazmand, 2002).

Turner and Hulme (1997: 106-131), the administrative reform is a universal way to bring change in the public sector on the grounds that the state will no longer be trusted, except in administrative reform, and divide it into 5 characters. Indeed, the reforms, most crucial of these is the fifth character in the development of human resources became the focus of reform, because to prove the quality of the performance of the bureaucratic apparatus (Levy, 2007). Elements of bureaucratic reform, reform indicates not only do the internal organizational bureaucracy, but also carried externally reforms which describe public participation as a form of government reform and even the government must undertake a reform of characteristics together on all fronts (Knott and Miller, 1987).

Turner and Hulme, opening up opportunities in administrative reform by the functioning of the various concepts of governance, namely the involvement of the three powers in the formulation of administrative changes in government (public, state and private parties). Reform-oriented change in attitude and behavior is also reinforced by Mosher in (Nasucha, 2004: 45) states that the content of administrative reform is the reorganization of the administration which is the main instrument of administrative improvements. The reform of administration will also produce changes in attitudes, behaviors and values of individuals. Thus the administrative reform includes institutional aspects and behavioral aspects.

Some way must be done in changing the administration of the government to solve their problems, among others, endurance or perseverance in serving the community, the organizers of the integrity and transparency of the body of bureaucratic organization and connectedness (Linden, 1994). As a consequence, efforts should be made fundamental reforms in the administration of public services, leaving paradigms, concepts and orientation of the old conventional public administration that were unfavorable to the society (Abdul Wahab, 2001).

Transparency is a fundamental aspect of good governance. with transparency will provide assurance of information distribution policy so as to facilitate the public and stakeholders to exercise control over governance (Dwiyanto et al, 2003: 129). Christensen (in Dwiyanto, 2003: 129) further said, an

important dimension in view of local government organizations, especially problems related to reform of the system is through transparency in government budgets. When the legislature can not work with the maximum and society cannot give feedback to their representatives, government work in conditions that are not controlled (Pramusinto, 2006: 7). , Steps to reform the bureaucracy mainly directed to improve the efficiency, transparency, and accountability of the bureaucracy (Lubis, 2001 in Dwiyanto, 2006: 60).

Implementation of the accountability of public services should be accountable to the public and the supervisor / head of service units of government agencies in accordance with the statutory provisions. environmental services should be orderly, organized, provided a comfortable waiting room, clean, tidy, beautiful environment and healthy and are equipped with services such as parking facilities, restrooms, places of worship, and others. (In Ratminto, 2009: 19-23, Zeithaml et al, 1990: 26, and Denhardt and Denhardt, 2003). One measure to see whether an organization providing a quality service cannot be seen real on the facilities and infrastructure of the organization, such as buildings, equipment, qualified and skilled staff, and have a means of communication (Zeithaml et al, 1990: 26).

3. Problem Definition

Based on the description in the background, the problems that occur are, "the low level of transparency of the administration of community health centers (puskesmas) in the five District / City of North Maluku Province".

4. Methodology

This study uses a survey approach. Survey research is research that takes a sample of the population and using questionnaires as the primary means of data collection (Singarimbun and Effendi, 1989: 1). Survey research is a quantitative research. The population in this study are all users of the service at the Public Health Center (Puskesmas) Regency / City by focusing on each study 1 (one) unit made in five (5) districts / cities in North Maluku province each District of South Halmahera, North Halmahera, Central Halmahera and Ternate. Multistage Random Sampling was used with various considerations based on the number of residents and representatives of community characteristics based tribal / ethnic. The survey has a margin of error of 7% at the 95% confidence level. According to Yamane, when the size of the population above 50,000 to 100,000 may be used a sample size of 204 with a 95% confidence level. (Yamane, 1967: 398-399).

Sampling using the multistage random sampling technique. The researchers chose the respondents in the study locations in five (5) existing health centers in five (5) regencies / cities in the province of North Maluku. The large number of samples taken in each district / city is determined by the population of the district / city in question. Data will be analyzed using descriptive analysis techniques on all respondents and connected with the rest of the items in question survey.

5. Results and Discussion

When asked of respondents associated with the service in health centers that require open service, 215 (71.66%) said that they felt, while respondents who claimed never a total of 32 (10.66%) votes, and who answered sometimes as many as 53 people (17.66%).

Of the 217 respondents who had felt their open service that has a different assessment levels also vary. A total of 128 (42.66%) claim If ever felt easy access, as many as 55 people (18.33%) say easily, and as many as 34 (11.33%) stated very easy procedure open services.

When respondents were asked about the cost of care in health centers in accordance with the standard

costs, a majority of 249 respondents (83%) said "yes", 36 respondents (12%) said "no" and 15 respondents (5%) said "do not know".

In providing a service charge at the health center in a transparent / open, as many as 236 respondents (78.66%) admitted "yes", while 54 respondents (18%) said "no" and 10 respondents (3.33%) to say "do not know".

When asked related to the need for changes to the bureaucratic system of health center services through transparency of health services at the health center, a total of 281 (93.66%) of respondents said "agree", 19 respondents (6.33%) undecided, and no respondents stated "disagree".

281 respondents who agree with the need to change the bureaucratic system of health center services through transparency of health services at the health center, provides a few different reasons. A total of 81 people reasoned, would "Changing the behavior of the personnel in the ministry", 91 respondents believe it would "provide facilities for services" and the majority of the 112 respondents reasoned realization "The commitment by bureaucrats to run the system". Respondents did not give any other reason.

Based on the results of the above opinion, the respondent has hope in efforts to reform the bureaucracy in the health service in North Maluku province. 109 Respondents stated that "the government bureaucracy as the organizer should be free from corruption"; 150 respondents expect "to the Ministry of Health conducted openly and fairly"; 41 respondents expect to be "concerned with the interests of public service is more important than the interests of a group / private", whereas the "Other" does not exist.

To realize these expectations, then the bureaucratic reform health care, as many as 246 respondent's requests in order to be responsible is "The central government / local", 48 respondents request that should be responsible is "Private / Companies", while "Others do not exist"

When the 300 respondents were asked related to health care in health centers conducted in a transparent procedure, as many as 199 respondents said "yes", 62 respondents said "no", and 39 respondents said "do not know".

6. Conclusion

In transparency, the majority of respondents still feels the service is open, but do not ignore the other respondents who claimed never to have felt it. Even that has seen no open service access due to the difficulty of access. Standardization costs already felt the majority of respondents in the aspect of transparency of health care costs (78.66%), but do not ignore the opinion of the respondents (18%) claimed lack of transparency in health care costs in health centers.

The idea of the changes in the bureaucratic system of health center services through transparency of health services at the health center, the majority (93.66%) wants to change the bureaucratic system more transparent with the desire to aspects of the commitment by bureaucrats to run the system, to provide facilities for services, changing behavior apparatus in service. Similarly, most respondent agree for health care to the community conducted openly and fairly (50%), Bureaucracy as the administrative machinery of government must be free from corruption (36%) and services related to the public interest is more important than the interests of a group / private (13, 66%). For this to materialize, the majority of respondents want to be responsible for reform of the health care bureaucracy is a central government / local (82%) and "Private / companies (18%)

7. Recommendations

Necessary to change the bureaucratic system of health center services through transparency of health services for the realization of the aspects of the commitment of bureaucratic apparatus in the running system, the urgency of the provision of care facilities, changed the behavior of the apparatus in service in North Maluku.

The health care process must be open and fair, the government bureaucracy as the host machine must be free of corruption and the importance of public interest, the central government / region should be more responsible in realizing the reform of health care bureaucracy.

Need transparent procedure's effectiveness in health care facilities is simple, straightforward, easy to understand and easy to implement with a flow chart that outlines the administrative requirements in accordance with the provisions of the legislation in order to facilitate access to services, determine service requirements, and the process of communication between officials and users can take place efficiently.

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